

The Value of BIM for Owners: A multi-stakeholder study focused on an office building

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Abstract

The Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry is characterized by its complexity and uniqueness that hampers digitalization and innovation. Additionally, the industry has been long struggling with challenges such as lacking collaboration and efficiency. Despite BIM playing an important role in the industry's digitalization, its wide-spread adoption has been rather slow, partially due to the lack of proof of value for private owners, who must be drivers for change.

This study presents, through a hybrid approach, tangible and intangible benefits profited by private owners by developing projects in BIM. The goal is to provide insights into how owners can potentialize savings in their projects by working in BIM. A qualitative study describes BIM enabled benefits from diverse perspectives in the industry, while a quantitative analysis results in the potential savings, in percentage of total construction cost, realized in the case study.

This dissertation begins with a comprehensive overview of the AEC industry's challenges and

stance on digitalization, specifically BIM adoption, as well as widely reported benefits from BIM project development that are indulged across the building's lifecycle. Subsequently, the case study which is the core of the analyses is described to provide context into the impact of each finding. A qualitative analysis based on semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders from the case study shed light onto BIM benefits perceived from diverse points of view within a project and onto specific savings enabled by BIM on the case study, and semi-structured interviews with private owners not related to the case study widen the understanding to broader contexts. Additionally, derived from findings in the qualitative analysis, a quantitative analysis presents the potential savings enabled by BIM in the case study, with results presented in percentage of the total construction cost.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/KgMX6CBzHw4>

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